

Colour changes induced by lamination on coated and uncoated offset prints

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Abstract—This study investigates colour changes induced by matte biaxially oriented polypropylene (BOPP) lamination on coated and uncoated offset prints. Colour differences were evaluated in the CIELAB colour space and analysed in terms of lightness (ΔL), chroma (ΔC), and hue (ΔH) components. The results showed that lamination produced substantial colour shifts on both substrates, with significantly larger changes observed on coated paper. Lightness and chroma were identified as the dominant contributors to the overall colour difference, whereas hue changes played a minor role. Correlation analysis revealed that the magnitude and direction of colour change depended on the initial colour attributes, particularly lightness. Spectral reflectance analysis further demonstrated that the optical response of laminated prints varied according to substrate type and colour characteristics. The findings confirm that matte lamination cannot be considered a colour-neutral finishing process and should therefore be taken into account in colour management and colour prediction of laminated printed products.

Keywords— Lamination, Colour changes, Offset printing, Colour management

I. INTRODUCTION

Colour reproduction is a critical quality requirement in printing and packaging industries because it directly influences product appearance, brand consistency, and consumer perception. In addition to the printing process itself, post-press finishing operations may significantly affect the final visual appearance of printed products. Among various finishing techniques, lamination is widely employed to improve abrasion resistance, moisture protection, durability, and aesthetic quality. Transparent polymer films such as glossy, matte, or silk laminates are commonly applied to printed surfaces to enhance product value and extend service life [1, 2].

Although laminate films are generally colourless, numerous studies have reported measurable colour shifts after coating or lamination. These colour changes are caused by modifications in the interaction between incident light and the printed surface rather than by changes in the ink layer itself [3–5]. Hoffstadt [2] proposed a model for predicting colour changes caused by coating based on the optical interaction between the coating layer and the printed substrate. Later studies showed that transparent coatings modify spectral reflectance through multiple internal reflections, refraction, and light-scattering phenomena occurring at the interfaces between air, coating layer, ink layer, and substrate [4, 5].

The optical mechanisms responsible for coating-induced colour changes have been extensively investigated over the last two decades. Simonot and Elias [3] reported that a transparent varnish layer may alter the perceived colour of printed surfaces through changes in the optical path of reflected light. More recently, Simonot et al. [4] introduced the concepts of halo effect and subsurface scattering in transparent coatings, demonstrating that light reflected from the substrate may propagate laterally within the coating layer and contribute to colour modifications. Based on these findings, Hébert et al. [5] showed that transparent coatings can significantly modify the appearance of halftone prints through both surface and subsurface optical phenomena. Their study showed that the application of a transparent coating can reduce lightness and increase chroma of halftone prints.

Several experimental investigations have confirmed the practical significance of these effects. Galić et al. [6] reported noticeable colourimetric changes in spot colours after UV varnishing, with some colour differences exceeding acceptable colour tolerances. Similar observations were reported by Cigula et al. [7],

who investigated colour reproduction on varnished cardboard packaging and demonstrated that varnishing can significantly affect colour reproduction in packaging prints. The influence of coating on optical print characteristics has also been studied by Hudika et al. [8], who observed measurable changes in colour coordinates and gloss properties depending on varnish coverage and surface conditions.

Recent studies have focused on understanding and predicting colour changes caused by transparent coatings. Dailliez et al. [9] investigated the impact of transparent coatings on the reflectance of halftone patterns and confirmed that coating-induced colour changes originate from modifications in spectral reflectance. In subsequent studies, the same authors employed multispectral microscopy to predict coated halftone reflectance [10] and analysed the influence of coating layers on the appearance of various halftone structures [11]. Their results provided further evidence that coating-induced colour changes depend strongly on the optical properties of the printed image and the interaction between the coating layer and the substrate. In particular, Dailliez et al. [12] demonstrated that matte and glossy coatings affect colour appearance differently, with matte finishes generally producing lighter and less saturated colours owing to increased surface light scattering.

Transparent coatings and laminates are known to affect colour appearance by modifying surface reflection, light scattering, and spectral reflectance. However, existing knowledge is still mainly derived from studies on selected spot colours, specific halftone structures, or colour prediction models. Systematic analysis using a large CMYK colour dataset remains limited, especially with respect to how lightness, chroma, and hue contribute to the overall colour difference on different paper substrates. Therefore, this study investigates colour changes induced by matte BOPP lamination using a 1485-patch ECI2002 colour target printed on coated and uncoated papers. The resulting colour shifts were analysed in terms of ΔE_{ab} , ΔL , ΔC , and ΔH , together with the relationships between the initial colour attributes and the corresponding changes after lamination.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

A. Sample preparation

To investigate lamination-induced colour changes, a 1485-patch colour chart (ECI 2002 target, Fig. 1) was printed using a Heidelberg Speedmaster SM102-4 sheet-fed offset press with Apex-G process inks (CMYK) on two types of papers including uncoated and coated papers (150 g/m²). The chart included a wide range of CMYK tonal combinations in order to represent the printable colour space. After printing, the sheets were conditioned under ambient laboratory conditions prior to further processing.

Fig. 1 ECI 2002 Characterization Target

The printed sheets were subsequently laminated using a thermal lamination process. A 25 μm biaxially oriented polypropylene (BOPP) matte film was applied as the laminating material. The film was bonded to the printed surface using an FM-380 laminating machine operated at 120 ± 2 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, allowing the adhesive layer to adhere to the paper substrate. The process was performed under uniform operating conditions to ensure consistent treatment of all colour patches

B. Colour measurement

Colour measurements were conducted using a MYIRO-1 spectrophotometer (Konica Minolta). All measurements were performed under D50 illumination with the 2° CIE standard observer. For each colour patch, spectral reflectance data were collected from 380 to 730 nm at 10 nm intervals, giving 36 spectral bands. The same measurement procedure was applied before and after lamination, thereby generating paired colour datasets for the original printed samples and their laminated counterparts.

The measured spectral data were converted into CIEXYZ tristimulus values and subsequently transformed into CIELAB colour coordinates. In the CIELAB system, L^* represents lightness, with lower values corresponding to darker colours and higher values corresponding to lighter colours. The a^* coordinate describes the green–red direction, whereas the b^* coordinate represents the blue–yellow direction. Negative a^* and b^* values indicate shifts toward green and blue, respectively, while positive values indicate shifts toward red and yellow..

Fig. 2 CIELAB color space

C. Colour difference analysis

The colour changes induced by lamination were evaluated using the CIE 1976 colour-difference formula (ΔE_{ab}), calculated from the CIELAB colour coordinates (L , a^* , b^*):

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{\Delta L^2 + \Delta a^2 + \Delta b^2} \quad (1)$$

where ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* represent the differences between the pre-laminated and post-laminated samples.

To further investigate the origin of the colour shifts, the overall colour difference was decomposed into lightness, chroma and hue components. The chroma value was calculated as:

$$C^* = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2} \quad (2)$$

and the chroma difference was determined by:

$$\Delta C = C_{post}^* - C_{pre}^* \quad (3)$$

The hue difference was calculated according to the CIE 1976 colour-difference framework:

$$\Delta H = \sqrt{\Delta E_{ab}^2 - \Delta L^2 - \Delta C^2} \quad (4)$$

where ΔL , ΔC and ΔH represent the contributions of lightness, chroma and hue variations, respectively.

To quantify the relative contributions of lightness, chroma and hue differences to the overall colour difference, the squared colour-difference components were normalized by the total squared colour difference:

$$p_L = \frac{\Delta L^2}{\Delta L^2 + \Delta H^2 + \Delta C^2} \times 100 \quad (5)$$

$$p_H = \frac{\Delta H^2}{\Delta L^2 + \Delta H^2 + \Delta C^2} \times 100 \quad (6)$$

$$p_C = \frac{\Delta C^2}{\Delta L^2 + \Delta H^2 + \Delta C^2} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta E^2 = \Delta L^2 + \Delta H^2 + \Delta C^2 \quad (8)$$

where p_L , p_H and p_C represent the relative contributions of lightness, hue, and chroma differences, respectively

The average contribution values reported in this study were obtained by averaging the individual contributions of all colour patches.

In addition, the relationships between the initial colour attributes and the corresponding colour changes after lamination were evaluated using Pearson correlation analysis. Correlations were calculated between the initial lightness (L^*) and the resulting lightness difference (ΔL), as well as between the initial chroma (C^*) and the corresponding chroma difference (ΔC), in order to investigate how the initial colour characteristics influence lamination-induced colour shifts.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Lamination-induced colour changes

The distributions of colour differences (ΔE_{ab}) induced by lamination are presented in Fig. 3, while the corresponding statistical parameters are summarized in Table I. The results demonstrate that lamination produced substantial colour changes on both coated and uncoated papers. The colour differences covered a wide range of values, indicating that the optical effect of the laminate film strongly depended on the colour being printed. For the entire dataset, numerous colour patches exhibited colour differences exceeding commonly accepted visual tolerances with 88% of the samples showing ΔE_{ab} values greater than 3,

confirming that lamination may significantly alter the perceived appearance of printed colours and should therefore be considered during colour management and process control.

TABLE I

SUMMARY STATISTICS OF COLOUR DIFFERENCES INDUCED BY LAMINATION (N = 1485 SAMPLES)

Metrics	Coated paper	Uncoated paper
Mean ΔE_{ab}	6.46	3.28
Median ΔE_{ab}	6.13	3.19
90th percentile ΔE_{ab}	10.49	4.63
Maximum ΔE_{ab}	19.71	17.96
% $\Delta E_{ab} > 3$	88%	57%
% $\Delta E_{ab} > 5$	63%	6%

Fig. 3 Statistical analysis of colour differences induced by lamination on coated (a) and uncoated paper (b)

Although colour shifts were observed on both substrates, their magnitude differed considerably. The mean colour difference on coated paper reached 6.46 ΔE_{ab} , nearly twice that measured on uncoated paper (3.28 ΔE_{ab}). Similar trends were observed for the median and 90th percentile values. Furthermore, 63% of the colour patches printed on coated paper exhibited colour differences greater than 5 ΔE_{ab} , whereas the corresponding proportion for uncoated paper was only 6%. These results indicate that lamination had a substantially stronger influence on colour appearance when applied to coated paper. The observed differences can be attributed to the distinct optical characteristics of the two paper substrates. Coated paper has a smoother and more optically uniform surface, allowing the printed ink layer to produce a relatively well-defined reflection response. When a matte laminate film is applied, the additional scattering introduced by the film substantially modifies the reflected light from the printed colour layer. As a result, the optical balance between the ink layer, substrate and laminate film is changed more clearly, leading to larger colour differences [9]. Meanwhile, uncoated paper already possesses a rougher and more porous surface with stronger diffuse scattering. Because its initial reflection behaviour is already highly scattering, the additional scattering effect introduced by the matte laminate film is less dominant. Consequently, the relative optical influence of the film is partially reduced, resulting in smaller colour changes on uncoated paper [7].

B. Contributions of lightness, chroma and hue differences

The distributions of the individual colour-difference components (ΔL , ΔH , and ΔC) and their relative contributions to the overall colour difference are presented in Fig. 4 and Table II. For both paper types, the colour shifts induced by lamination were primarily associated with changes in lightness and chroma, whereas hue differences contributed only a minor fraction of the total colour difference.

TABLE III
SUMMARY OF LIGHTNESS, CHROMA AND HUE DIFFERENCES INDUCED BY LAMINATION (N=1485 SAMPLES)

Metrics	Coated paper	Uncoated paper
Mean ΔL	3.3	2.5
Mean ΔH	1.4	1.1
Mean ΔC	4.4	1.3
Contribution of ΔL (%)	38.4	61.2
Contribution of ΔH (%)	10.0	18.0
Contribution of ΔC (%)	51.5	20.8

Fig. 4 Distributions and relative contributions of lightness, chroma, and hue differences to the overall colour difference after lamination for coated (a) and uncoated (b) papers

For coated paper, the mean absolute differences in lightness, hue, and chroma were 3.3, 1.3, and 4.4 units, respectively. Chroma exhibited the largest variation among the three colour attributes and accounted for an average of 51.5% of the total colour difference. Lightness contributed an additional 38.4%, while hue

contributed only 10.0%. These results indicate that the dominant effect of lamination on coated paper is an increase or decrease in colour saturation and lightness rather than a significant shift in hue.

A different behaviour was observed for uncoated paper. The mean absolute values of ΔL , ΔH , and ΔC were 2.5, 1.1, and 1.3 units, respectively. For uncoated paper, lightness became the dominant contributor to the overall colour difference, accounting for 61.2% of ΔE_{ab} . Chroma and hue contributed only 20.8% and 18.0%, respectively. Although lamination still altered colour saturation, its influence on chroma was considerably weaker than that observed on coated paper.

The different contribution patterns observed for the two substrates are mainly associated with differences in the chroma response to lamination. Colours printed on coated paper generally possess higher colour saturation because of improved ink holdout and reduced light scattering within the substrate. Consequently, the introduction of a nearly neutral laminate film produces more pronounced chroma modifications, making ΔC the dominant contributor to the overall colour difference. In contrast, the lower saturation and stronger intrinsic scattering of uncoated paper reduce the magnitude of chroma changes after lamination. Under these conditions, lightness variations become relatively more important and dominate the overall colour difference, accounting for more than 60% of the observed ΔE_{ab} .

In summary, for both coated and uncoated papers, lamination primarily modified lightness and chroma, resulting in noticeable shifts in perceived colour appearance. However, the magnitude and direction of these changes were not straightforward and appeared to depend on the initial colour attributes and substrate characteristics. Therefore, the relationships between the initial lightness and chroma values and their corresponding changes after lamination are further analysed in the following section.

C. Relationship between colour shift and initial colour attributes

To further investigate the mechanisms responsible for lamination-induced colour changes, the relationships between the initial colour attributes and the corresponding signed colour-difference components were examined. Fig. 5 presents the variations of the lightness difference ($\Delta L = L_{\text{post}} - L_{\text{pre}}$) and chroma difference ($\Delta C = C_{\text{post}} - C_{\text{pre}}$) as functions of the initial lightness and chroma values for coated and uncoated papers.

The behaviour of the lightness component differed substantially between the two substrates. For coated paper (Fig. 5a), a strong negative correlation was observed between the initial lightness and the resulting lightness difference ($r = -0.79$). Dark colours generally exhibited positive ΔL values and became noticeably lighter after lamination, whereas colours with high initial lightness showed predominantly negative ΔL values and became slightly darker. The transition between these two behaviours occurred at approximately $L^* = 45$. This result indicates that the optical effect of the laminate film strongly depends on the initial reflectance level of the printed colour. The observed trend can be explained by the additional reflection and scattering introduced by the matte BOPP film. For dark colours with low reflectance, the additional scattered light represents a relatively large increase in reflected energy, leading to a significant increase in perceived lightness. In contrast, for light colours, where the reflectance is already high, the same optical interaction results in a slight reduction in lightness. Representative spectral measurements shown in Fig. 6 support this interpretation by demonstrating broad reflectance changes over the visible wavelength range following lamination.

On the other hand, the relationship between L^* and ΔL for uncoated paper was considerably weaker ($r = -0.14$). Most colours exhibited negative ΔL values across the entire lightness range, indicating that lamination generally reduced the lightness of colours printed on uncoated paper. The relatively weak correlation suggests that the magnitude of the lightness change was only weakly governed by the initial lightness. This behaviour is likely related to the inherently rough and porous surface of uncoated paper, which already produces substantial diffuse scattering before lamination and therefore reduces the relative influence of the laminate film on the reflected light distribution.

Fig. 5 Relationships between initial colour attributes and lamination-induced changes: L^* versus ΔL and C^* versus ΔC for coated (a) and uncoated papers (b)

Fig. 6 Representative reflectance spectra of two low-chroma colours printed on coated paper: (a) low-lightness colour and (b) high-lightness colour

The chroma component showed a broadly similar behaviour for both coated and uncoated papers. As shown in Fig. 5, ΔC values were distributed on both the positive and negative sides, indicating that lamination could either increase or decrease colour saturation depending on the printed colour. The largest chroma changes were mainly observed in the medium-chroma region, approximately $C^* = 30\text{--}50$, whereas colours with very low or very high chroma generally exhibited smaller ΔC values. This indicates that the chroma response to lamination was not governed simply by the initial chroma value.

For coated paper, the overall linear correlation between C^* and ΔC was weakly negative ($r = -0.18$), while for uncoated paper a weak positive correlation was obtained ($r = 0.35$). However, the scatter plots reveal that these correlation coefficients do not fully describe the behaviour of the data, since both positive and negative ΔC values were observed across a wide chroma range. Therefore, the direction and magnitude of chroma change are likely influenced by the combined effects of chroma, lightness, and the spectral shape of the printed colour rather than by C^* alone.

The combined effects of lightness and chroma changes explain the overall colour differences reported in Section III-B. For coated paper, the largest colour shifts were generally observed in dark and highly saturated colours, where substantial changes in both ΔL and ΔC occurred simultaneously. This finding is consistent with the contribution analysis, which showed that chroma and lightness accounted for approximately 52% and 38% of the total colour difference, respectively. In contrast, colour shifts on uncoated paper were dominated by lightness changes, which contributed more than 60% of the total ΔE_{ab} , while chroma changes remained comparatively small.

Overall, the results demonstrate that lamination-induced colour shifts arise from the combined modification of both lightness and chroma, and that the relative importance of these effects depends strongly on the substrate. Coated paper exhibits stronger and more systematic optical changes due to the laminate film, whereas the rougher surface of uncoated paper moderates these effects and reduces their dependence on the initial colour attributes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated the influence of matte BOPP lamination on colour appearance of offset printed samples on coated and uncoated papers. The results confirmed that lamination produced noticeable colour shifts on both substrates and therefore cannot be considered a colour-neutral finishing process. The effect of lamination depended strongly on the paper substrate. Coated paper showed a more pronounced colour response, while uncoated paper exhibited a weaker overall colour change. The observed shifts were mainly governed by variations in lightness and chroma, whereas hue changes played only a minor role.

The analysis also showed that the initial colour attributes influenced the direction and magnitude of the colour change. In particular, lightness was an important factor in explaining the spectral response after lamination. The results provide a better understanding of the optical mechanisms responsible for lamination-induced colour shifts and may support the development of colour prediction and compensation strategies for laminated printed products.

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